

Coronavirus/COVID 19

**CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR VIOLATION OF QUARANTINE
REGULATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SPREAD OF
COVID-19**

Oleh M. Omelchuk*, Nataliia M. Plysiuk*, Lesia V. Omelchuk, Anna
V. Danilova***, Viacheslav A. Moroz******

Abstract: Coronavirus (COVID-19) is the latest dangerous infectious disease in the world, which appeared in late 2019. The purpose of this study is a systematic legal analysis of criminal liability for violation of quarantine regulations in Ukraine. Attention is focused on Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, which makes provision for liability for violation of sanitary rules and regulations for the prevention of infectious diseases and mass poisoning. For this study, the main method used is the normative analysis of the law (doctrinal analysis). The analysis allowed to conclude that the schemes of liability for violations of quarantine norms in European countries are very diverse. The first group includes countries that have established responsibility for the infection, including through negligence, and the second – countries that criminalise violations of regulations aimed at combating the spread of infectious diseases.

Keywords: Covid-19 Pandemic; Liability for Quarantine Violations; Prevention of Infectious Diseases; Criminal Offence; Isolation; Quarantine; Social Distancing

* Department of Criminal Law and Procedure, Leonid Yuzkov Khmelnytskyi University of Management and Law, 29000, 8 Heroyiv Maydanu Str., Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine

** Department of Public Management and Administration, Leonid Yuzkov Khmelnytskyi University of Management and Law, 29000, 8 Heroyiv Maydanu Str., Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine

*** Department of Constitutional, Administrative and Financial Law, Leonid Yuzkov Khmelnytskyi University of Management and Law, 29000, 8 Heroyiv Maydanu Str., Khmelnytskyi, Ukraine

**** Department of Surgery, National Pirogov Memorial Medical University, Vinnytsya, 21018, 56 Pyrohova Str., Vinnytsia, Ukraine

Introduction

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis has affected all spheres of public life around the world. The main measures in preventing the spread of the disease in society are hand hygiene, social distancing and quarantine. Such measures may include: complete or partial closure of educational establishments and workplaces; limitation of the number of visitors and contacts between residents of special establishments, such as long-term care facilities and prisons; cancellation, prohibition and restriction of mass gatherings and private meetings; internal or external closure of borders; and restrictions on movement for entire regions or countries. This has led to a drastic change in daily life due to anti-virus rules and compliance with anti-epidemic restrictions, ranging from stay-at-home orders and restrictions on public gatherings to punishment for assaulting health workers¹.

E.S. Barnert² points out that the susceptibility of prisons and detention centres to COVID-19 challenges the well-being of all children affected by the justice system. L. Burris³ and J. Bresler⁴ emphasise that even during the COVID-19 pandemic, the penitentiary system opposes the changes required to facilitate the response to the pandemic and address the issue of early release, while the police have committed themselves to physical distancing and other health measures⁵. R. L. Phillips⁶ emphasises the additional difficulties caused by the

-
- 1 W.B. Amar, N. Karray, M. Zribi and S. Maatoug. "Criminal medical liability in the context of COVID-19 pandemic". *La Tunisie Médicale* (2020), 98(5): 334-342; J.M. Miller and A. Blumstein. "Crime, justice & the COVID-19 pandemic: toward a national research agenda". *American Journal of Criminal Justice* (2020), 45: 515-524. doi: 10.1007/s12103-020-09555
 - 2 E.S. Barnert. "COVID-19 and youth impacted by juvenile and adult criminal justice systems". *Pediatrics* (2020), 146(2): e20201299.
 - 3 S. Burris, S. de Guia, L. Gable, D.E. Levin, W.E. Parmet and N.P. Terry. *Assessing legal responses to COVID-19*. (Boston: Public Health Law Watch, 2020). Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3675919> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3675919>
 - 4 J. Bresler and L. Beletsky. COVID-19, incarceration, and the criminal legal system. (2020). Retrieved from <https://events.networkforphl.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/COVID-19-Incarceration-and-the-Criminal-Legal-System.pdf>
 - 5 K. Nowotny, Z. Bailey, M. Omori and L. Brinkley-Rubinstein. "COVID-19 exposes need for progressive criminal justice reform". *Home American Journal of Public Health (AJPH)* (2020). Retrieved from <https://ajph.aphapublications.org/doi/full/10.2105/AJPH.2020.305707>
 - 6 R.L. Phillips and L. Abi-Falah. "Criminal responsibility for the COVID-19 pandemic in Syria". (2020). Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3664268>

counteraction of COVID-19 during military conflicts. S. Taak⁷ notes that the COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic has affected each country differently and how long this impact will last is unknown.

In many European countries, notably Italy and Spain, administrative and criminal penalties have been used to strengthen the lockdown regime and applied in cases of serious violations against quarantine measures that contributed to the spread of the pandemic (both intentional and negligent), such as those with a confirmed diagnosis COVID-19, which did not comply with the requirements for self-insulation¹. I. Freckelton² also examines the borrowing of provisions on public health by Australian criminal legislation and its compatibility with conventional principles of criminal justice³. Most states indicate that quarantine violations can be committed intentionally or negligently (this form of guilt can be expressed in both self-confidence and negligence)⁴. Ukrainian scientists also pay attention to certain aspects of criminal law counteraction to the spread of coronavirus. For example, A. Vozniuk and S. Cherniavskiy⁵ fragmentarily analyse this issue. The aim of this study is a systematic legal analysis of the issue of criminal liability for violation of quarantine norms in Ukraine.

Materials and Methods

Conventionally, the methods of legal research can be divided into quantitative and qualitative. And while quantitative issues do not usually arise, qualitative methods are a more complex issue in science. However, both Ukrainian and foreign researchers in the publications do not pay enough attention to the

-
- 7 S. Taak. "International criminal court and liability of China during COVID-19". *International Journal of Law* (2020), 6(4): 276-278.
 - 1 L. Foffani. "COVID-19 outbreak, criminal law and role of the EU". *European Criminal Law Review* (2020), 10(2): 13-139. doi: 10.5771/2193-5505-2020-2-137
 - 2 I. Freckelton. "COVID-19: criminal law, public assemblies and human rights litigation". *Journal of Law and Medicine* (2020), 27(4): 790-806.
 - 3 Yu. Endang, T. Susilawati and P. Budi. "Law compliance against perpetrators of COVID-19's forced retrieval". *Pena Justisia Media Komunikasi dan Kajian Hukum* (2020), 19(1): 82-89. doi: 10.31941/pj.v19i1.1137
 - 4 V. Turanjanin and D. Radulovic. "Coronavirus (COVID-19) and possibilities for criminal law reaction in Europe". *Iranian Journal of Public Health* (2020), 49(1): 4-11. doi: 10.18502/ijph.v49iS1.3664
 - 5 A. Vozniuk and S. Cherniavskiy. "Violation of COVID-19 prevention rules and regulations: current issues of criminal and administrative liability". *Ūriddičnij Časopis Nacional'noi Akademii Vnutrišnih Sprav* (2020), 19: 8-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33270/04201901.8>.

issues of methodology when using qualitative research methods, which leads to a decrease in confidence in the research⁶. As D. Smith⁷ points out, classical legal research is the process of gathering and analysing facts, identifying and resolving legal issues, finding, analysing, and synthesising legal powers, and determining whether a law is effective. Many researchers, such as Lieggi⁸, point out the inadmissibility of a situation where the methods of the social sciences displace the legal ones. Instead, in the study of phenomena that constitute the subject of the study of criminal law, quantitative and qualitative methods should complement each other.

A. Giubilini⁹ points out that systematic analysis is the basis for conducting classical legal research. Based on this analysis, the scientist can identify the conceptual basis of the legal provision, study the principles and make some suggestions for reforms. In essence, modern legal methods are analytical. However, the actual research in the field of law involves careful analysis and creative synthesis of various legal provisions, doctrines and evaluation of laws, and must be combined with analytical skills and deduction and induction. Therewith, scholars often use inductive methods of legal research, based on the circumstances of cases decided by courts. At the same time, analytical research should not be seen as lower or higher than positivist research.

M.I.P. Mohamed notes that the classic method of legal research is a normative analysis of law (doctrinal analysis), which involves trying to understand the best balance of rights and responsibilities within the framework set by legislation. The analysis is built around the question of how it should be¹. A. Giubilini² points out that the most common variant of the above method of legal research in Europe is the IRAC method (acronym term meaning the method

6 N. Semchuk, S. Lykhova and U. Demianenko. "Using English as a foreign language when teaching subjects of the criminal law cycle". *The Asian International Journal of Life Sciences* (2019), 21(2): 517-534.

7 D. Smith and M. Ryan. "International postal, quarantine and safety regulations". *Microbiology Australia* (2019), 40(3): 117-120.

8 C. Lieggi. Importation and quarantine. In: *The Zebrafish in Biomedical Research: Biology, Husbandry, Diseases, and Research Applications*, pp. 431-442. (Amsterdam: Elsevier, 2019).

9 A. Giubilini, T. Douglas, H. Maslen and J. Savulescu. "Quarantine, isolation and the duty of easy rescue in public health". *Developing World Bioethics* (2018), 18(2): 182-189.

1 M.I.P. Mohamed, I.J. Jamal, S.N.T.S. Mohammad, D. Pakianathan and S.M. Attalla. "Ethical review for the legal healthcare strategies implemented during pandemics". *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine* (2020), 7(11): 542-550.

2 A. Giubilini, T. Douglas, H. Maslen and J. Savulescu. "Quarantine, isolation and the duty of easy rescue in public health". *Developing World Bioethics* (2018), 18(2): 182-189.

of legal analysis, which comprises problem statement (Issue), Rule (analysis of regulations governing this issue), Application (the study of the practice of application of legislation), and formulation of conclusions (Conclusion). Considering the above, for the purposes of this study, which constitutes a classical legal analysis of criminal law, classical normative analysis of the law (doctrinal analysis) and its variant known as the IRAC method will be used as the main method of study.

Results and Discussion

According to the chosen IRAC method, the analysis should begin with a statement of the issues (Issue). In this case, the purpose of this article is a systematic legal analysis of the issue of criminal liability for violation of quarantine regulations in Ukraine. For such a systematic analysis, the formula is known in Ukrainian criminal law, which is the “composition of a criminal offence”, will be used, which includes such elements as an object, objective side, subject, and subjective side. As for the Rule part – the analysis of regulations governing this issue – it is worth noting the following. Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine³ as amended by Law No. 530-IX⁴, was to operate for three months from the date of publication of the Law, considering the changes introduced by Law No. 540-IX of March 30, 2020.

Analysis of other provisions of the Criminal Code of Ukraine allows concluding that if the violation of quarantine norms was committed by a person intentionally to weaken the state, it will qualify under Article 113 of the Criminal code of Ukraine as “Diversion”. After all, the text of Article 325 of the Criminal Code indicates that the terms “quarantine” and “epidemic” are not directly used in the text of the above article. It is only a matter of violating certain rules and regulations (which are not necessarily quarantine restrictions) to prevent infectious diseases (which is also not always associated with the adoption of appropriate acts that give the spread of a disease the official status of an epidemic). This position of the legislator is quite controversial because the changes to Article 325 were temporary in nature to counteract the violation of quarantine restrictions caused by the epidemic of a particular disease.

3 Law of Ukraine No. 2341-III “Criminal Code of Ukraine”. (2001). Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2341-14#Text>

4 Law of Ukraine No. 530-IX “On amendments to certain legislative acts of Ukraine aimed at preventing the occurrence and spread of coronavirus disease (COVID-19)”. (2020). Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/530-20#n22>

Instead, Article 113 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, which makes provision for liability for sabotage, punishes a number of actions aimed at weakening the state, including actions aimed at spreading epidemics, epizootics, and epiphytosis. Therewith, both epidemics (explosive spread of infectious human diseases) and epizootics (explosive spread of infectious animal diseases) and epiphytosis (rapid spread of infectious plant diseases) involve the introduction of certain quarantine measures. Therefore, theoretically, in violation of quarantine norms aimed at counteracting the epidemic, these actions should be considered both in terms of qualifications under Article 113 and under Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. The main feature that will help to distinguish such actions, in this case, is the purpose of the criminal offence. Sabotage presupposes a definite purpose as a mandatory feature – the weakening of the state and only a deliberate form of guilt. Furthermore, to qualify an offence under Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, the purpose does not matter, and actions can be made both intentionally, and negligently.

Article 325 is placed in Section 13 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, i.e., the legislator considers the generic object of this offence to be the health of the population. The direct object of this crime is the procedure for preventing infectious diseases and poisoning, which is contained in certain rules and regulations. From an objective point of view, it is a crime with a material component. Therefore, its mandatory features are: the act, expressed in the form of violation of rules and regulations established to prevent epidemic and other infectious diseases, as well as mass non-communicable diseases (poisoning) and control them; consequences, which means the spread of these diseases or the creation of a threat of such spread; the causal link between them, which is a direct link between the act and the consequences.

The analysis of the content of the article indicates that the relevant norms can be violated both by action (holding a mass event contrary to the ban) and by inaction (non-compliance with the mask regime). In this case, the analysed provisions are blanket; therefore, to identify what are the violations of rules and regulations established to prevent epidemic and other infectious diseases, as well as mass non-communicable diseases (poisoning) and control them, it is necessary to examine the documents in which these rules and regulations are set. In Ukraine, for the period of the coronavirus pandemic, such documents are the Law of Ukraine “On Protection of the Population from Infectious

Diseases” of April 6, 2000¹ and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 211 “On Prevention of Spread of COVID-19 Coronavirus” of March 11, 2020².

From the analysis of these legislative acts it can be concluded that the prohibited acts include, in particular: being in public places without wearing personal protective gear; movement by a group of persons in the amount of more than a specified number of persons, except in certain permitted cases; conducting mass (cultural, entertainment, sports, social, etc.) events, except those permitted; work of business entities, which makes provision for the reception of visitors in cases where the planned measures make provision for restrictions on their work; regular and irregular transportation in case of a ban on their implementation, etc. Regarding the consequences, it should be noted that the components of the analysed criminal and related administrative offences are quite close, because in cases of violation of quarantine rules it is extremely difficult to distinguish these actions, as they are both violations of sanitary rules and regulations on infectious disease prevention³. However, it is the consequences, as part of the objective side of the criminal offence, that is key to distinguishing it from administrative.

A. Vozniuk⁴ notes that in the theory of criminal law, the question of who can be the subject of this crime is debatable. Some scientists believe that the subject is special, and it can only be a person responsible for compliance with these anti-epidemic rules. Others point out that in the context of a pandemic and quarantine restrictions, everyone has certain responsibilities for compliance with special rules; therefore, in special circumstances, it is advisable to talk

1 Law of Ukraine No. 1645-III “On protection of the population from infectious diseases”. (2000). Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/1645-14#Text>

2 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine No. 211 “On prevention of the spread of coronavirus COVID-19 in Ukraine”. (2020). Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/211-2020-%D0%BF#Text>

3 A.V. Iatsyshyn, V.O. Kovach, Y.O. Romanenko, I.I. Deinega, A.V. Iatsyshyn, O.O. Popov, Yu.G. Kutsan, V.O. Artemchuk, O.Yu. Burov and S.H. Lytvynova. “Application of augmented reality technologies for preparation of specialists of new technological era”. *CEUR Workshop Proceedings* (2020), 2547: 181-200; K. Tsaras, I.V. Papatnasiou, V. Vus, A. Panagiotopoulou, M.A. Katsou, M. Kelesi and E.C. Fradelos. “Predicting factors of depression and anxiety in mental health nurses: a quantitative cross-sectional study”. *Medical Archives (Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)* (2018), 72(1): 62-67. doi:10.5455/medarh.2017.72.62-67

4 A. Vozniuk and S. Cherniavskiy. “Violation of COVID-19 prevention rules and regulations: current issues of criminal and administrative liability”. *Ūrīdīčnij Časopis Nacional'noi Akademii Vnutrišnih Sprav* (2020), 19: 8-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33270/04201901.8>.

about the general subject of the crime. Vozniuk notes that Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine mainly punishes holding public events during quarantine (primarily religious – from the consecration of Easter cakes in a bakery to holding public events), the organisation of such events by persons with symptoms of the COVID-19 disease; the operation of markets under established restrictions; concealment of information about the COVID-19 disease, etc.

An intermediate conclusion is that the general provision of the Criminal Code of Ukraine aimed at criminal law counteraction to violation of quarantine restrictions in Article 325. Temporary wording of Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine made provision for liability for an offence that can be committed both by action and inaction. The crime is registered as material. The subject of crime is common. From a subjective standpoint, the specified criminal offence may be committed intentionally or negligently. The practice of applying this study mainly made provision for the responsibility for holding mass events during the operation of the relevant ban and concealment of information about the disease on COVID-19. The results of the study are best compared with the work of A. Vozniuk¹, who analyses similar issues in Ukraine but focuses on other aspects, and the study by Turanjanin & Radulović², where scientists conduct a similar analysis for certain EU countries. The conclusions obtained in the study generally correspond to the conclusions reached in the analysis of Vozniuk. Comparison with the conclusions obtained by Turanjanin & Radulović is a more complex process, as these scientists have analysed the legislation of many countries, which is why their study is described by a greater breadth of coverage, but less detail of the analysis. Given the above, this study will focus on comparing some of the most relevant provisions.

Turanjanin & Radulović³ notes that there are two articles in the Criminal Code of the Kingdom of Norway that relate to violations of quarantine norms. Article 237 makes provision for the punishment for contracting an infectious disease of any person who infects or exposes another person to the risk of contracting an infectious disease dangerous to public health, including

-
- 1 A. Vozniuk and S. Cherniavskiy. "Violation of COVID-19 prevention rules and regulations: current issues of criminal and administrative liability". *Ūridičnij Časopis Nacional'noi Akademii Vnutrišnih Sprav* (2020), 19: 8-19. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33270/04201901.8>.
 - 2 V. Turanjanin and D. Radulovic. "Coronavirus (COVID-19) and possibilities for criminal law reaction in Europe". *Iranian Journal of Public Health* (2020), 49(1): 4-11. doi: 10.18502/ijph.v49iS1.3664
 - 3 Ibid.

through negligence. The commission of such a criminal offence is considered a qualified crime if it has led to the general spread of the disease or the risk of such spread, or loss of life or significant harm to the health of the victim⁴. Paragraph 192 of the Danish Penal Code stipulates that any person who acts contrary to the provisions of a law or regulation adopted in pursuance of a law to prevent or control infectious diseases and thereby creates a risk of the spread of such a disease shall be punished. The Swedish legislature makes provision for liability for the spread of infectious diseases, i.e., causing danger to human life or health through the transmission or spread of a serious infectious disease. The Finnish Criminal Code in Chapter 34 identifies a number of actions as a threat to health, including the spread of dangerous infectious diseases⁵.

The Criminal Code of the Czech Republic makes provision for punishment under two separate articles for the spread of human diseases. Article 152 punishes anyone who intentionally infects a person or increases the risk of spreading infectious human diseases. Article 153 deals with the negligent spread of human infectious disease⁶. The Bulgarian legislature stipulates in Article 355 of the Criminal Code that a person who violates an order issued against the spread or emergence of an infectious disease that affects humans shall be subject to punishment. If the act was committed during an epidemic or is related to the death of the victim, the penalty is increased¹.

That is, the comparison of criminal liability for violating quarantine norms in Ukraine and other European countries suggests that many countries are trying to resist such encroachments through criminal law. The schemes offered for this purpose differ in considerable variety. However, they can be divided into several groups. The first group includes countries that have established responsibility for the transmission of infectious diseases, including through negligence, and the second – countries that criminalise violations of regulations aimed at combating the spread of infectious diseases. These two models are quite close but have some differences. And if in case of violation of quarantine norms by healthy or conditionally healthy persons is not criminally punished, then in the second case the responsibility of healthy persons violating quarantine

4 Ibid.

5 Ibid.

6 Ibid.

1 V. Turanjanin and D. Radulovic. "Coronavirus (COVID-19) and possibilities for criminal law reaction in Europe". *Iranian Journal of Public Health* (2020), 49(1): 4-11. doi: 10.18502/ijph.v49iS1.3664

(if it indirectly promotes diseases) can be punished. Therefore, the second model can be considered more rigid. Ukraine, which punished violations of the rules and regulations established to prevent epidemic and other infectious diseases, can be considered a typical representative of the second model. In many countries, countering the COVID-19 pandemic has led to significant restrictions on human rights. Freedom of assembly was most restricted, and people were in fact many weeks in conditions corresponding to house arrest.

Conclusions

From the objective standpoint, the act stipulated by Article 325 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, is a crime with material structure. Its obligatory features include: action (in the form of action or inaction), expressed in the form of violation of rules and regulations established to prevent epidemic and other infectious diseases, as well as mass non-communicable diseases (poisoning) and control them; consequences, which means the spread of these diseases or the creation of a threat of such spread; the causal link between them, which constitutes a direct link between the act and the consequences.

From the comparison of criminal liability for violation of quarantine provisions in Ukraine and other European countries, it can be concluded that the proposed schemes are very diverse. However, they can be divided into two groups. The first group includes countries that have established responsibility for the transmission of infectious diseases, including through negligence, and the second – countries that criminalise violations of regulations aimed at combating the spread of infectious diseases. The second model can be considered more rigid. Ukraine, which punished violations of the rules and regulations established to prevent epidemic and other infectious diseases, can be considered a typical representative of the second model.